

Nutritional Enhancement of White Bread Using Little Millet Flour and Papaya Leaf Powder: A Comprehensive Analysis of Proximate Composition and Physico-Chemical Properties

Bharathi. P¹, Malathy S*^{1,2}

¹*Department of Food Technology, Hindustan Institute of Technology and Science, Padur, Kelambakkam, Chennai 603103, Tamil Nadu, India.*

²*Department of Bioinformatics, Sathyabama Institute of Science and Technology, Rajiv Gandhi Salai, OMR, Sholinganallur, Chennai 600119.*

*Corresponding author : Malathy S

ABSTRACT:

This research aimed to improve the nutritional value of white bread through the use of underutilized plants, specifically papaya leaf powder (PLP) and little millet flour (LMF). Three formulations were tested: S0 (control 65% Refined Wheat Flour), S1 (30:30:1 ratio of Refined Wheat Flour, LMF, and PLP), and S2 (20:30:1 ratio of Refined Wheat Flour, LMF, PLP). The bread was prepared using ingredients such as Refined Wheat Flour, LMF, PLP, Psyllium Husk, Corn Starch, Butter, Salt, Sugar, Fat, and Milk Powder. The prepared bread underwent various analyses including Proximate (Moisture, Protein, Fat, Ash, Crude Fiber, and Carbohydrates), Microbiological (Total Bacterial Count, Yeast and Mold Count), Physio-Chemical (pH, Titratable Acidity, and Water Holding Capacity), Antioxidant Test (DPPH assay), Shelf Life (self-assessed), and Sensory Evaluation by a panel of judges from Hindustan Institute of Technology and Science. All tests were performed in triplicate. Results indicated that S1 was dominant and was highly favored by consumers. In conclusion, enriched bread with LMF and PLP significantly enhanced antioxidant levels, shelf life, total energy, and sensory attributes like flavor, taste, and texture. This novel-functional product offers promising health benefits.

Keywords: Antioxidant, Enriched bread, Little Millet, Papaya Leaf, Sensory, Shelf Life.

I. INTRODUCTION

Bread is the food that humans eat the most, so it is important to ensure the product's primary quality attributes and biosafety and chemical safety¹. Among the cereals used for domestic consumption, millet is the most ancient. Millet is more nutritionally dense and rich in health-promoting compounds than other staple cereal crops². Furthermore, millets are classified as an environmentally friendly crop because they are C4 cereal grains that absorb more carbon dioxide from the atmosphere and release more oxygen³. The year 2023 has been designated as the International Year of Millet by the Food and Agricultural Organizations (FAO). One of the minor millets in the Poaceae family is the little millet (*Panicum sumatrense* L.). It is a native crop of Karnataka and is grown all over India. Although small, little millet has a high nutritional content despite being small. In addition to being a great source of B vitamins, it is also a great source of copper, iron, zinc, and potassium⁴. Little millet, also referred to as "Tribal Millet" and the "King of Cereals," is primarily consumed by tribe members. It is a non-perishable food that promotes healthy eating among consumers and stores well⁵. Patients with cardiovascular and vascular disorders and those with diabetes should consume these grains. Little millet grain has great storage qualities and, when stored under normal circumstances, can be kept for several years without worrying about store grain pests⁶. Little millet's low glycemic index can be attributed to its high dietary fiber content. *C. papaya* L., also referred to as papaya, pawpaw, and kates, is a member of the Caricaceae family⁷. Due to its antidiabetic and anti-cancer effects, as well as its antioxidant qualities, papaya's phytochemicals when retained in significant amounts are good for your health⁸. A limited number of studies have documented the antiseptic qualities of fresh papaya leaves, whereas dried leaves can be utilized as a blood purifier and aid in better digestion. Papaya leaf juice has recently been found to have strong anticancer properties⁹. Papaya leaves are a useful nutritional supplement because they are high in proteins, fats, vitamins, and carbohydrates¹⁰. The significance of carrying out the requisite descriptive investigations to ascertain the safety of consuming papaya leaves is additionally underscored concerning their utilization in the healthcare domain¹¹. The primary goal of this study is to investigate the physiochemical and microbiological components of white bread and increase its nutritional value by using underutilized plants, particularly papaya leaf powder (PLP) and little millet

flour (LMF).

Fig1: Graphical abstract of enriched bread

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

This chapter lists all the raw materials and processing techniques used for the development of the product, analytical products, and methodologies followed for the sensory Evaluation at the various stages of research for the fulfillment of objectives.

A. Ingredients:

Ingredients such as Little millet flour, Refined Wheat Flour, and papaya leaf powder were bought from a big basket. Yeast, salt, sugar, butter, and milk powder were procured from Krishna super market Kelambakkam, Chennai.

B. Formulation

Table 1 below illustrates how different levels of little millet flour were combined with refined wheat flour to make the enriched bread.

TABLE1: FORMULATION OF RAW MATERIAL

Sample	Refined Wheat Flour %	LMF %	PLP %	Yeast %	Corn Starch %	Psyllium husk%	Milk powder%	Butter %	Sugar %
S0	65	0	0	2	0	0	3	5	25
S1	30	30	1	2	2	2	3	5	25
S2	20	30	1	2	9	5	3	5	25

C. Method Of Preparation :

The bread was prepared based on¹² and as shown in Fig 2. All the ingredients were weighed using a weighing machine. 5 grams of dry yeast was combined with water and sugar and left to ferment for approximately 8 minutes. The dry ingredients (refined wheat flour, small amounts of millet flour, milk powder, sugar, corn starch, psyllium husk, and butter) are combined with a dough mixer. Wet ingredients such as fermentation yeast were combined to form dough. The mixing time was approximately 10 minutes. After the dough was mixed, it was left for an hour to proof. The dough was mixed with papaya leaf powder after an hour, and it was then left to proof again for an additional hour in a bread mold. Papaya leaf is added during the second proofing because it has a lower fermentation activity. After the second proofing, the bread mold was placed in a preheated oven and baked for 30 minutes at 210°C. The bread was placed on a wire rack to cool after baking. The bread was then cut into slices.

Fig2: Flow chart of preparation of enriched bread

D. Proximate Analysis

Using AOAC International-approved protocols, the flour's moisture, ash, fat, protein, and fiber contents were examined in triplicate (AOAC, 2000). Carbohydrate was estimated by difference¹³.

Proximate Analysis, comprising moisture, protein, ash, fat, and crude fiber, was performed on both the control and samples by using AOAC 2000 method¹⁴. The accessible carbohydrates were calculated after subtracting other preset proximate characteristics such as fat content, protein, and crude fiber. The remainder were carbohydrates.

Carbohydrates % = (% Protein+% Fat+ %Ash+% moisture+%crude fibre).

E. Physio-chemical Analysis

- 1) *pH analysis*: A digital pH meter that had been calibrated with pH 4 buffer solution was used to measure the pH. A 30 milliliter sample was poured into a 50 milliliter beaker. The pH reading was recorded once the beaker was gently swirled until the probe was inserted into the sample and the pH reading stabilized.
- 2) *Water holding capacity*: 30 ml of water was added to 10 g of the dough, which was then placed in a centrifuge tube. For every twenty minutes, it was mixed five times. After that, the dough was centrifuged for ten minutes. After removing the sample, the water that was left over was measured and put into a beaker. The residue remaining in the centrifuge tube was measured. Following that, the formula was used to calculate the dough's water-holding capacity.

Water holding capacity % = $\frac{\text{weight of the sample after centrifugation} - \text{dry sample weight}}{\text{Dry sample weight}}$

Dry sample weight

- 3) *Titrateable Acidity*: 20 milliliters of distilled water were combined with 10 grams of homogenized dough. Next, the suspension was moved into a conical flask with a capacity of 250 ml. For indication purposes, two drops of phenolphthalein were added. Subsequently, the prepared solution was titrated in comparison to a 0.1N NaOH solution. The titration was carried out until a pink hue emerged, at which point the value was recorded. The amount of lactic acid generated in the sample as a consequence of fermentation was then computed.

$$\text{TA} = \text{Titre Value} \times 0.09 \times 100\%$$

Where, Titre Value = Volume of sample solution used

0.09 is a conversion factor

F. Microbiology Analysis

Microbiological tests, such as total bacterial count and yeast and mold count, were performed to study the microbiological status of the samples. The total bacterial count was conducted using the Method IS 5402:2012, while yeast and mold counts were performed according to IS 5403:1997.

G. Antioxidant Test

The DPPH assay involved preparing a 15 mM DPPH solution, mixing 100 μl of PLP extract with 100 μl of DPPH stock solution, and incubating for 30 minutes at 37 °C in the dark. The absorbance drop was measured at 517 nm. Results were expressed as mmol Trolox equivalents (mmol TE) per g of PLP.

H. Shelf Life Analysis

The shelf life analysis was self-assessed. The breads were checked at the Room temperature condition (25°C -28°C). The shelf life analysis was carried out until the bread was spoiled.

I. Sensory Analysis

A hedonic scale with nine points was used for the sensory analysis. The analysis was performed by the staff and students of Hindustan Institute of Technology and Science. An analysis was conducted on the parameters, which included appearance, texture, color, aroma, flavor, and overall acceptability.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Proximate Analysis

Table: 2 below shows the composition of various bread samples. The mean of the moisture content varied between 33.83 to 44.03. The mean value of the protein content varied between 8.47 to 9.65. Similarly for the crude fibre was 0.48 to 0.46. Similarly, the fat content is 1.01 to 1.98. The ash content was between 0.29 to 1.58. The carbohydrate content was between 1.22 to 1.92. The Proximate parameters such as moisture was low in sample 1(33.83), the crude fiber content of sample 1 is 0.8 which is high when compared to sample S0 and sample S2, protein content was high in sample 0 (9.65), the fat content of sample 1 (1.22) was found to be the lowest among all, the ash content was high in sample 1 (1.36) and the carbohydrates were high in sample 1 (81.67).

TABLE2: PROXIMATE ANALYSIS

Sample	Moisture %	Protein %	Crude Fibre%	Fat %	Ash %	Carbohydrates %
S0	44.03±0.80 ^c	9.65±0.50 ^a	0.48±0.13 ^a	1.92±0.08 ^a	1.36±0.15 ^a	80.18±0.27 ^c
S1	33.83±0.95 ^b	9.04±0.73 ^b	0.86±0.08 ^a	1.22±0.22 ^a	0.92±0.05 ^a	81.67±0.62 ^c
S2	33.83±0.06 ^b	8.47±0.83 ^b	0.66±0.14 ^a	1.80±0.15 ^a	1.08±0.69 ^a	81.36±0.51 ^c

B. Physio – Chemical Analysis

The physio-chemical values in Table3 indicates that the highest pH value was found on S1(5.17) and the lowest value on S0(4.88) . The pH values decreasing suggest that the composite flour is of high quality, which lowers the microbiological load¹⁵. The titrable acidity was high in S2 (0.90) when compared to S1(0.40) and S0(0.77). Higher titrable acidity in bread typically indicates that there is a higher level of acidity present in the bread dough. This could be due to various factors such as prolonged fermentation. It can influence the flavor, texture, and overall quality of the bread. The water holding capacity was high in S0 (64.67%) when compared to S1(40.66%) and S2(39.67%). Increased WHC levels have been associated with an increase in amylose leaching and solubility as well as a decrease in starch crystalline structure¹⁶. One measure of the amount of water available for gelatinization in flour is its water absorption capacity (WAC)¹⁷.

TABLE 3. PHYSIO-CHEMICAL

Samples	pH	Titrateable Acidity	Water Holding Capacity (%)
S0	4.88±0.32 ^a	0.77±0.11 ^a	64.67±0.59 ^a
S1	5.17±0.36 ^a	0.40±0.17 ^a	40.66±0.37 ^b
S2	4.89±0.05 ^a	0.90±0.07 ^a	39.67±0.65 ^b

C. Microbiology Analysis

Microbiological analysis was determined after the enriched bread baking tests, i.e. 6 h after baking. The TBC and YMC were expressed as CFU/g. The highest bacterial count was found in S0 (450) and the lowest Bacterial Count was found in S1 (310). The highest yeast and mold count was found in S0 (100) which decreased to 50 and 40 in both the enriched samples S1 and S2.

TABLE 4: MICROBIOLOGY ANALYSIS

Samples	Total Bacterial Count (CFU/g)	Yeast and Mould Count (CFU/g)
S0	450	100
S1	310	50
S2	360	40

D. Antioxidant Test

The result in Table 5 shows that with the increase in papaya leaf powder, there is an increase in the antioxidant properties. When compared with S0 and S1, S0 (3.9%) has very less antioxidant properties. Similarly, the antioxidant value was double the S0 value in S1(77%). S2 (75.3%) has lower antioxidants than S1. Similar findings were observed, with the percentage of antioxidant activity in papaya leaf cookies treated T0, T1, and T2 not significantly increasing, but significantly increasing in the T3 treatment¹⁸. This indicates that an increase in papaya leaf powder concentration will result in a rise in the antioxidant value.

TABLE 5: ANTIOXIDANT TEST

Samples	Method	Result %
S0	DPPH	3.9
S1	DPPH	77
S2	DPPH	75.3

E. Sensory Analysis

The sensory analysis was performed by the staff and students of the Hindustan Institute of Technology and Science. The sensory attributes were carried out using 9 point Hedonic Scale 9- like extremely, 8- like very much 7- like moderately, 6- like slightly 5- neither like not dislike, 4- dislike slightly, 3- dislike moderately, 2- dislike very much, 1- dislike moderately. Compared to samples S0 and S1, the mean value of the appearance in the S0 and S1 samples was greater than in sample S2. Furthermore, sample S0 received higher scores for the color and texture than the enriched bread. However, the aroma, taste, and overall acceptability score were higher in sample S1, when compared to other samples S0 and S2.

TABLE 6: SENSORY ANALYSIS

Sample	Appearance	Colour	Texture	Aroma	Taste	Overall Acceptability
S0	8.9 ± 0.17^{cd}	8.7 ± 0.35^{bc}	8.9 ± 0.05^c	7.43 ± 0.40^{cd}	8.0 ± 0.4^{ab}	8.8 ± 0.26^{bcd}
S1	8.86 ± 0.15^{bcd}	8.7 ± 0.2^{bc}	8.7 ± 0.26^b	9.63 ± 0.15^d	9.34 ± 0.35^{cd}	9.0 ± 0.17^{cd}

S2	8.7 ± 0.14^{bcd}	8.8 ± 0.23^{bcd}	8.7 ± 0.43^b	9.06 ± 0.21^{cd}	8.8 ± 0.26^{bcd}	8.9 ± 0.25^{cd}
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F. Shelf Life Analysis

Every bread sample was assessed for its shelf life at room temperature (between 25 and 28°C), without any interruptions. Organoleptic evaluation was carried out for all the three samples, until they mould formation. There was an increase in their sourness and acidic odour day by day. A greenish discoloration was observed in S0 on the third day along with the plentiful growth of molds. The odor emitted from S0 was very mild. A mild sour odor was emitted from S1. A slight greenish colour was observed on the 6th day. A darkish-green and black and white discoloration was noticed on the surface of S2 on the 7th day. Since S1 and S2 has more fiber, it may absorb moisture and slow down enzymatic reactions, thereby preserving the bread's freshness for a longer duration. Among the three samples, S0 got spoiled to a greater extend than S1 (lesser) and S2 (least). This indicates that the shelf life of the bread will increase with an increase in PLP concentration.

IV. CONCLUSION

In the current study, Little millet flour and papaya leaf powder bread was prepared using three different concentrations (S0, S1, S2). The S1 sample showed considerably better proximate and physio-chemical properties than the other two samples. The sensory attributes of flavor, taste, and texture were also dominant in the S0, with the S1 having a value similar to it. As a result, the S1 sample is regarded as superior to the S2. In a similar vein, S1's antioxidant value was high and double that of S0. In a nutshell, when bread is enriched with little millet flour and papaya leaf powder, a significant enhancement is seen in the levels of antioxidants shelf life, total energy and sensory attributes like flavour, taste, texture and overall acceptability. Patients with diabetes are the primary audience for this enriched bread. The combination of all of these characteristics results in a novel, functional product with promising health benefits.

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